

Indira Sona, the first rice hybrid for the shallow lowlands of India's Chhattisgarh State

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Chhattisgarh is known as the rice bowl of India. Rice is grown on 3.7 million ha of land in the state. However, average rice productivity in the state is quite low (1.3 t ha^{-1}). Since the state's creation in 2000, 11 high-yielding rice varieties have been released for commercial cultivation for the different agroecological zones.

The rainfed lowland ecosystem occupies about 40% of the state's total rice area. Yield in these areas has remained stagnant in the past decades. Several pockets within this system can be considered as favorable lowland. The adoption of rice hybrids in such areas, along with proper crop management practices, can increase rice productivity in the state. The IGKV has identified the first rice hybrid, Indira Sona, for the shallow lowland ecosystem. Released for commercial cultivation in 2006, it was also endorsed by the Central Variety Release Committee in 2007 (Fig. 1). The hybrid has medium growth duration and high yield potential ($8\text{--}9 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$) (table). The area under hybrid rice is increasing gradually in the state and is currently around 50,000 ha.

Fig. 1. Indira Sona rice hybrid

Morphological and grain characteristics of Indira Sona.

Days to 50% flowering	90–95 d
Days to maturity	125–130 d
Tillering ability	High (15–20)
Panicle length (cm)	26.5 (mean)
Spikelets panicle ⁻¹	243 (mean)

Dehulled grain length (mm)	7.1 (av)
Dehulled grain width (mm)	2.05 (av)
Length/breadth	3.43 (av)
Aroma	Mild
Alkali value	6.0
Amylose content (%)	20.90
Grain chalkiness	Occasionally present
Grain type/rice grade	Long slender
Milling percentage	78.72 (av)
Head rice percentage	55.0 (av)
1,000-grain weight (g)	25.6 (av)
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	6–6.5 t ha ⁻¹
Potential yield (t ha ⁻¹)	8–9 t ha ⁻¹
Reaction to diseases and insect pests	
Gall midge	Resistant
Blast	Moderately resistant

Seed production of Indira Sona is easier because it involves less staggered flowering between the female and male parental lines (5–7 d). The restorer line (R710-437-1-1) has good floral characters—i.e., asynchronous flowering with good pollen load. Thus, only two staggered sowings of the restorer line are required for seed production. The panicle of restorer line R710-437-1-1 is pale green at the time of flowering; the sickle-shaped bunt at the end of the panicle is one of the restorer's distinguishing features (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Spikelets of restorer line R710-437-1-1

The hybrid is expected to spread quite fast, particularly in the northern hill zone and gall midge-prone areas of the central plain region.